

Online Creativity in the Global Innovation Index

Angelo Leogrande, LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU,
leogrande.culture@lum.it

In the context of the Global Innovation Index (GII), "Online Creativity" represents a country's ability to leverage digital platforms to create, share, and monetize creative content, innovations, and intellectual property. This dimension reflects how actively a nation participates in the digital ecosystem to foster creativity, innovation, and entrepreneurial activity. It focuses on how countries use the internet and digital tools to generate creative works, ranging from websites and apps to multimedia content such as videos and blogs. A key aspect of online creativity is the registration of domain names, both country-specific and generic. A high number of domain registrations indicates a strong online presence and reflects the dynamism of a country's digital and entrepreneurial landscape. This metric highlights the digital footprint of businesses, individuals, and institutions in the online world, signaling the country's ability to engage with and create digital content. Additionally, the production of online content, such as websites, blogs, and activity on social media, is a fundamental component of online creativity. Countries with high levels of user-generated content demonstrate the ability to foster a vibrant digital environment where creativity can thrive. The creation and dissemination of digital content reflect not only individual creativity but also the accessibility and use of technology within society. The development of mobile applications is another crucial indicator of online creativity. The number of apps developed by residents shows how much a country is integrating technology into daily life and promoting innovation within the digital economy. Moreover, video uploads on platforms like YouTube measure engagement in online media production. A high volume of video uploads indicates the country's involvement in global media, highlighting its contribution to the evolving digital creative landscape. These indicators provide a comprehensive view of a nation's capacity to participate and thrive in the global digital economy through creative online innovation. The data covers the period from 2013 to 2022.

Online Creativity in 2022. The data related to "Online Creativity" in the Global Innovation Index 2022 highlights a significant disparity between countries in terms of their ability to generate creative content in the digital space. At the top of the rankings are countries such as Iceland, Switzerland, and the Netherlands, which score very high (63.6, 61, and 60.5 respectively), demonstrating an advanced digital ecosystem and a strong capacity to seize opportunities offered by the online world for innovation and creativity. These countries likely benefit from a combination of solid technological infrastructure, favorable government policies, and high digital literacy, which enables citizens to actively participate in online content creation. Luxembourg (57.9) and Hong Kong (56.3) closely follow, showing that even small states can excel in online creativity if supported by advanced technological infrastructures and targeted policies. Hong Kong, in particular, stands out as an interesting example of an Asian tech hub, ranking among the top globally due to its vibrant tech and creative scene. The dominance of European and Asian countries at the top of the list reflects the centrality of investments in innovation and digitalization, which play a crucial role in global competitiveness. Countries such as Cyprus (47.9), Singapore (45.6), and Germany (45.2) are found mid-ranking. While they perform well, there is still room for improvement compared to global leaders. These nations have good technological infrastructure and a solid foundation to support online creativity, but they could do more to facilitate broader participation in digital production and encourage startups and creative businesses to thrive in the online space. It is interesting to note that

traditionally advanced innovation powerhouses, such as the United States (43) and the United Kingdom (44.8), rank relatively lower compared to global leaders. This may reflect a growing gap between the adoption of digital technologies for creativity versus other, more established technological fields. For example, the U.S. score could result from a highly diversified economy where the digital sector plays a significant but not dominant role compared to other industrial areas. Toward the lower end of the rankings, countries like Italy (15.5), South Korea (15.1), and Spain (19.9) are well below the global averages of the most advanced countries in terms of online creativity. Italy, in particular, despite its rich cultural and creative tradition, seems to struggle to transfer this heritage to the digital realm, likely reflecting structural deficiencies in access to digital technologies, support policies, and investment in technological innovation. At the very bottom, we find many developing countries, such as Bangladesh (0.9), Nigeria (0.7), and Ethiopia (0.1), with extremely low numbers. The presence of these countries at the lowest positions highlights the significant challenges they face in terms of digital infrastructure, internet access, and their ability to participate in the global online creativity market. These countries suffer from limited digital technology adoption, as well as economic and social issues that restrict citizens' ability to express themselves creatively online. In conclusion, the data shows a strong correlation between economic development, technological infrastructure, and online creativity. Economically advanced countries tend to dominate the rankings, while developing countries struggle to establish themselves in this field. However, even among developed countries, there are significant differences, suggesting that adopting specific policies to encourage online creativity can make a difference in a country's position in this global ranking.

Online creativity between 2013 and 2022. The data on online creativity, which covers a wide range of countries between 2013 and 2022, shows a general decline in the online creativity index for most nations. This drop is quite surprising considering the growing importance of digital technology in everyday life and the continuous expansion of technology on a global scale. Analyzing the percentage variations, a uniform trend of significant reduction emerges, with some countries experiencing much steeper declines than others. In particular, many Western and developed countries, which have historically enjoyed strong digital infrastructure and online creativity, have registered a worrying decrease. For example, Germany saw a drop of 34.4%, the United Kingdom 40.66%, and the United States as much as 30.76%. This could be indicative of market saturation or a decline in support for online creativity in these countries. Even Nordic countries like Sweden, which boasted a very high rate in 2013 (71.4%), saw a drastic drop of over 35%. Another group of countries, mostly developing or emerging, experienced even more significant percentage declines. Italy, for instance, recorded a drop of 70.97%, while countries like Spain (-62.02%), Poland (-62.73%), and Greece (-70%) had similar results. These data suggest a loss of momentum in online creativity in many nations that may not have adequately invested in digital infrastructure or the training necessary to stimulate online creativity. The most extreme decline is observed in developing and less industrialized countries. Nations like Bangladesh (-92.31%), Kenya (-90.97%), and Yemen (-98.41%) show a sharp regression. In these cases, the decline could be attributed to various factors, including limited internet access, weak technological infrastructure, political or economic instability, and a lack of incentives for developing digital skills and online creativity. Interestingly, some countries with strong tech economies, such as South Korea and Japan, recorded significant declines (-56.86% and -70.42%, respectively), despite their reputation as global tech hubs. This might suggest a diversification of creative interests, with more focus on offline innovations or sectors outside the digital realm, or even digital market saturation, which limits further growth in online creativity. On the other hand, there are some notable exceptions, such as Singapore, which recorded only a small decline of 0.44%. This

could be attributed to a consistent policy of supporting digital innovation and creativity, combined with solid infrastructure and a technology-based economy. The fact that Singapore has maintained high levels of online creativity over time underscores the importance of national strategies and targeted investments in this sector. Overall, these data paint a picture of a global decline in online creativity, which seems to hit developing countries the hardest, but also affects many developed countries. Online creativity, once seen as one of the most promising frontiers for economic and cultural growth, appears to be going through a phase of contraction, possibly linked to market saturation, infrastructural challenges, or a decrease in public and private investment in the digital sector.

Conclusions. The value of online creativity decreased on average between 2013 and 2022 from 33.6 units to 13.2 units, equivalent to a reduction of -60.66%. The top-performing countries during this period (2013-2022) are: Singapore with -0.44%, Belarus with -13.68%, Cyprus with -16.55%, Switzerland with -17.01%, and Hong Kong with -19.57%. The worst-performing countries are: Tanzania with -98.65%, Tajikistan with -98.89%, Madagascar with -98.92%, Togo with -99.13%, and Angola with -99.15%.

Database: Global Innovation Index,

<https://prosperitydata360.worldbank.org/en/indicator/WIPO+GII+224> , Accessed 13 October 2024.

Performance	Countries	2013	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
Top Performers	Singapore	★ 45,8	★ 45,6	★ -0,2	★ -0,44
	Belarus	★ 23,4	★ 20,2	★ -3,2	★ -13,68
	Cyprus	★ 57,4	★ 47,9	★ -9,5	★ -16,55
	Switzerland	★ 73,5	★ 61	★ -12,5	★ -17,01
	Hong Kong SAR, China	★ 70	★ 56,3	★ -13,7	★ -19,57
Worse Performers	Tanzania	★ 7,4	★ 0,1	★ -7,3	★ -98,65
	Tajikistan	★ 18	★ 0,2	★ -17,8	★ -98,89
	Madagascar	★ 9,3	★ 0,1	★ -9,2	★ -98,92
	Togo	★ 22,9	★ 0,2	★ -22,7	★ -99,13
	Angola	★ 11,7	★ 0,1	★ -11,6	★ -99,15

References

- Leogrando, A., Saponaro, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). A GIS based estimation of quality of life in Italian regions. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR) e-ISSN*.
- Costantiello, A., & Leogrando, A. (2023). The Impact of Research and Development Expenditures on ESG Model in the Global Economy. Available at SSRN 4414232.
- Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., Angelo, L., & Matarrese, M. M. (2023). The intellectual assets in Europe. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 27(2), 1-13.
- Magazzino, C., & Leogrando, A. (2021). Subjective well-being in Italian regions: A panel data approach. *Applied econometrics and international development*, 21(1), 1-18.
- Leogrando, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The attractiveness of European research systems. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(10), 72-101.
- Costantiello, A., & Leogrando, A. (2023). The Role of Political Stability in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. Available at SSRN 4406997.
- Leogrando, A. (2023). The Rule of Law in the ESG Framework in the World Economy. Available at SSRN 4355016.
- Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrando, A. (2023). The Role of Government Effectiveness in the Light of ESG Data at Global Level. Available at SSRN 4324938.
- Leogrando, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The impact of R&D investments on corporate performance in European Countries. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(7), 186-201.

Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Labor Force Participation Rate in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. Available at SSRN 4466452.

Angelo, L., Laureti, L., & Alberto, C. (2022). The Innovation Index in Europe. Available at SSRN 4091597.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Enterprises Providing ICT Training in Europe. Available at SSRN 4021150.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., Leogrande, A., & Matarrese, M. (2021). The Innovation Linkages in Europe. Available at SSRN 3983218.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Ease of Doing Business in the ESG Framework at World Level. Available at SSRN 4420946.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Voice and Accountability in the ESG Framework in a Global Perspective. Available at SSRN 4398483.

Leogrande, A. (2022). Mortality from Cancer in the Italian Regions. *International Web Post*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Satisfaction with the Environmental Condition in the Italian Regions between 2004 and 2020. Available at SSRN 4061708.

